

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

„GREEN ECONOMY“ – THE MODERN GLOBAL PARADIGM FOR A SUSTAINABLE FUTURE

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Abstract

The article discusses the green economy as a modern paradigm of socio-economic development of the world. In today's era, the issue of green economy and sustainable development has taken a big role in the background of global challenges.

The relevance of the existing problematic issue in its turn derives from the essence of sustainable development, because it plays the main role in the issue of economic growth, while the interests of future generations must be protected.

The article also shows the essence, advantages and main objectives of the green economy.

A comparative analysis of green and brown economic models is also given.

Also, we've conducted a comprehensive study analysing the most and least green countries globally.

Keywords: Green Economy, Sustainable Development, Renewable Energy, Brown Economy.

Main Text

The green economy is a component of the innovative economy, the development of which only became possible once the world reached a corresponding level of innovative development. This includes effective innovative policies, an innovative system, technological knowledge, financial resources, and more.

The green economy represents a relatively new direction in economic science and practice, which acknowledges the dependence of the economy on nature and views it as an integral part of nature. It combines issues of sustainable development and ecological economics.

The green economy ensures the long-term enhancement of human well-being and the reduction of inequality, allowing future generations to avoid essential risks of environmental degradation.

For building the economy, both economic development and economic growth are necessary, but economic development is becoming increasingly decisive. It is precisely the qualitative changes in the economy, namely innovative development, that provide the opportunity to transition to a "green" economy, as this process requires radical changes in all elements of the economic system.[2]

The term "green economy" was first used in the "Green Economy Project", and the concept was presented in the document of the 2012 Rio de Janeiro Conference on Sustainable Development, entitled "The Future We Want". [4]

The green economy is an economic framework that aims to promote sustainable development by focusing on reducing environmental risks, enhancing resource efficiency, and fostering a balance between economic growth and environmental protection.

Here's a more detailed overview

Key Principles of Green Economy: [1]

1. Resource Efficiency:

- **Objective:** To reduce the consumption of natural resources and minimize waste.

- **Approach:** Encouraging practices that optimize the use of resources, such as energy and water conservation, recycling, and sustainable agriculture.

2. Environmental Protection:

- **Objective:** To mitigate the negative impacts of human activities on the environment.

- **Approach:** Implementing policies and technologies that reduce pollution, combat climate change, and protect ecosystems and biodiversity.

3. Sustainable Development:

- **Objective:** To achieve long-term economic growth while maintaining environmental health and social equity.

- **Approach:** Balancing economic activities with ecological sustainability to ensure that natural resources are available for future generations.

4. Green Investments:

- **Objective:** To drive economic growth through investments in green technologies and industries.

- **Approach:** Supporting and incentivizing investments in renewable energy, green infrastructure, and sustainable innovation.

5. Job Creation:

- **Objective:** To generate employment opportunities in sectors that contribute to environmental sustainability.

- **Approach:** Creating green jobs in areas such as renewable energy, energy efficiency, and environmental management.

6. Social Equity:

- **Objective:** To promote social inclusion and reduce inequalities.

○ **Approach:** Ensuring that the benefits of the green economy are accessible to all, including marginalized communities, and that economic opportunities are fairly distributed.

Benefits of a Green Economy:

- **Environmental Health:** Reduces pollution, conserves natural resources, and protects ecosystems, contributing to a healthier planet.

- **Economic Growth:** Stimulates new industries and technologies, creating job opportunities and enhancing competitiveness.

- **Social Well-being:** Improves quality of life through cleaner air and water, and more sustainable living conditions.

Challenges and Considerations:

- **Infrastructure:** Developing and maintaining green infrastructure, such as renewable energy systems and efficient public transportation.

- **Policy and Regulation:** Crafting effective policies and regulations that support green practices and incentivize sustainable behavior.

- **Public Awareness:** Educating individuals and businesses about the benefits of the green economy and how they can contribute.

The green economy represents a shift towards an economic system that harmonizes economic activities with environmental stewardship and social equity, aiming for a sustainable and prosperous future. The green economy encompasses various sectors that focus on sustainability, resource efficiency, and reducing environmental impacts.

Here's an overview of **key sectors within the green economy:** [3]

1. Renewable Energy

- **Focus:** Generating energy from renewable sources such as solar, wind, hydro, geothermal, and biomass.

- **Benefits:** Reduces reliance on fossil fuels, lowers greenhouse gas emissions, and promotes energy security.

- **Examples:** Solar panels, wind turbines, hydroelectric power plants, and geothermal energy systems.

2. Energy Efficiency

- **Focus:** Improving the efficiency of energy use in buildings, transportation, and industry.

- **Benefits:** Reduces energy consumption, lowers costs, and minimizes environmental impacts.

- **Examples:** Energy-efficient appliances, LED lighting, smart grids, and energy-efficient building designs.

3. Sustainable Transportation

- **Focus:** Promoting transportation methods that are less harmful to the environment and more energy-efficient.

- **Benefits:** Reduces emissions, decreases traffic congestion, and improves air quality.

- **Examples:** Electric vehicles (EVs), public transit systems, cycling infrastructure, and car-sharing programs.

4. Green Building and Construction

- **Focus:** Designing and constructing buildings

that are environmentally friendly, resource-efficient, and sustainable.

- **Benefits:** Reduces energy and water usage, minimizes waste, and creates healthier living and working environments.

- **Examples:** LEED-certified buildings, green roofs, sustainable materials, and energy-efficient construction techniques.

5. Waste Management and Recycling

- **Focus:** Efficiently managing and recycling waste to minimize landfill use and resource depletion.

- **Benefits:** Reduces waste, conserves resources, and prevents pollution.

- **Examples:** Recycling programs, composting, waste-to-energy technologies, and circular economy practices.

6. Water Conservation and Management

- **Focus:** Protecting and efficiently managing water resources to ensure their availability and quality.

- **Benefits:** Ensures sustainable water supply, reduces pollution, and supports ecosystem health.

- **Examples:** Water-efficient fixtures, rainwater harvesting, wastewater treatment, and sustainable water management practices.

7. Agriculture and Food Systems

- **Focus:** Promoting sustainable agricultural practices and food production systems that minimize environmental impact.

- **Benefits:** Enhances soil health, reduces pesticide use, and supports biodiversity.

- **Examples:** Organic farming, sustainable agriculture, precision farming, and local food systems.

8. Eco-Tourism and Sustainable Travel

- **Focus:** Encouraging tourism practices that respect the environment and support local communities.

- **Benefits:** Preserves natural and cultural heritage, supports conservation efforts, and benefits local economies.

- **Examples:** Eco-lodges, wildlife tours, and responsible travel practices.

9. Green Finance

- **Focus:** Providing financial products and services that support environmental sustainability and climate resilience.

- **Benefits:** Mobilizes capital for green projects, reduces financial risks associated with environmental issues, and promotes sustainable investment.

- **Examples:** Green bonds, sustainable investment funds, and impact investing.

10. Environmental Services

- **Focus:** Providing services that protect and improve environmental quality.

- **Benefits:** Enhances ecosystems, improves public health, and supports environmental conservation.

- **Examples:** Environmental consulting, conservation planning, and ecosystem restoration.

Each of these sectors plays a critical role in advancing the green economy by addressing different aspects of sustainability and contributing to a more resilient and equitable future. Top of Form

The traditional type of economy, which is based on the use of exhaustible and non-renewable resources (fuel), is often referred to in the scientific literature as the **"brown" economy**. It is associated with high concentration of carbon in production processes, wasteful consumption of resources and social exclusivity, in

contrast to the "green" economy, which has a low carbon content, characterized by rational consumption of resources and social inclusiveness.

A comparative analysis of the green economy and the brown economy highlights their differing approaches to economic development, environmental impact, and sustainability.

A detailed comparison is shown here: (Table 1)

Table 1

The Comparative analysis of green and brown economic models [3]

Basic criteria	„Brown Economy“ (traditional Economy)	„Green Economy“
Definition and Core Principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition: An economic model characterized by high reliance on fossil fuels and traditional industries with significant environmental impact and resource depletion. • Core Principles: Focus on short-term economic growth, often at the expense of environmental and social considerations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition: An economic system aimed at reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcities while promoting sustainable development without degrading the environment. • Core Principles: Sustainability, resource efficiency, low environmental impact, and social equity.
Environmental Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Impact: Associated with significant environmental harm, including high levels of pollution, deforestation, greenhouse gas emissions, and resource depletion. • Examples: Fossil fuel extraction, coal-fired power plants, and large-scale industrial agriculture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental Impact: Designed to minimize environmental degradation by promoting renewable energy, efficient resource use, and reducing pollution. Aims to protect ecosystems and biodiversity. • Examples: Renewable energy projects, energy-efficient technologies, and sustainable agriculture.
Economic Growth and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic Growth: Often prioritizes rapid economic expansion and industrialization, sometimes at the cost of environmental and social concerns. • Development Focus: Short-term gains in economic growth may overshadow long-term sustainability and environmental health. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic Growth: Promotes sustainable growth by investing in green technologies and practices that provide long-term economic benefits while protecting the environment. • Development Focus: Balances economic growth with environmental sustainability and social equity, aiming for a holistic improvement in quality of life.
Resource Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource Management: Characterized by extensive resource extraction and consumption with minimal regard for long-term sustainability. Often leads to resource depletion and environmental degradation. • Approach: Linear economy principles, focusing on "take, make, dispose" models. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource Management: Emphasizes the efficient and sustainable use of resources, promoting recycling, conservation, and the use of renewable resources. • Approach: Circular economy principles, reducing waste, and enhancing resource productivity.
Social Impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Impact: Can lead to social and environmental injustices, including health problems from pollution, and often lacks equitable distribution of economic benefits. • Focus Areas: Short-term economic gains may come with adverse effects on vulnerable populations and communities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Impact: Aims to enhance social equity by creating green jobs, improving public health, and ensuring that environmental benefits are widely shared. • Focus Areas: Fair labor practices, community involvement, and health benefits from reduced pollution.
Innovation and Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation: May focus on traditional technologies and industries that are less environmentally friendly, with limited emphasis on sustainability. • Examples: Conventional energy sources, industrial machinery with high emissions, and non-recyclable materials. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation: Encourages technological innovation that supports sustainability, such as renewable energy technologies, green infrastructure, and sustainable materials. • Examples: Solar panels, electric vehicles, and energy-efficient appliances.

<p>Policy and Regulation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy: Often characterized by limited environmental regulations and subsidies for fossil fuels and resource-intensive industries. • Examples: Tax incentives for fossil fuel industries, lax environmental regulations, and minimal investment in green technologies. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy: Supported by policies and regulations that promote environmental protection, resource efficiency, and sustainable development. • Examples: Green taxes, emissions trading schemes, and environmental regulations.
<p>Long-Term Viability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-Term Viability: May face challenges due to unsustainable practices leading to environmental crises, resource shortages, and economic instability. • Future Outlook: Risks include climate change impacts, resource depletion, and environmental degradation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-Term Viability: Aims for long-term sustainability by addressing climate change, conserving resources, and fostering resilience in economies and ecosystems. • Future Outlook: Promotes adaptation and mitigation strategies to ensure future generations can thrive.

Being “green” reflects how much a country cares about preserving and restoring the natural environment and its resources, as well as the health of its citizens. This is shown through policymaking and the effectiveness of current measures.

However, as we’ll see, some countries prioritise the environment more than others.

We’ve conducted a **comprehensive study analysing the most and least green countries globally**. We combined and compared 4 different reports, namely the Environmental Performance Index (EPI)¹ from Yale University, a report from the EU’s Joint Research Centre (JRC)², the Green Future Index (GFI)³ from Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), and the IQAir⁴ information platform. [6]

European countries dominate the top 10 list.

According to the latest rankings, Denmark has emerged as the greenest country globally, thanks to its robust environmental policies and commitment to renewable energy. Following closely are the United Kingdom and Finland, both known for their sustainable practices and high environmental standards.

The top 10 greenest countries are as follows: (Pic.1)

1) Sweden

Coming in at first place is Sweden. Sweden ranks highly across the studies, coming in 5th place on the EPI, 9th for the GFI, and 4th for the lowest annual average PM2.5 concentration at **6.6 µg/m³**.

However, like most European countries Sweden’s main downfall is its CO2 emissions per capita, ranking only 28th place with **4.18 tonnes** (4th in Europe). Known for its innovation in renewable energy, Sweden has an EPI score of 72.7, highlighting its effective environmental policies.

Some of Sweden’s highlights are that it has a perfect score in the EPI for protecting marine ecosystems

and it ranks second in the GFI’s *CO2 emissions growth in transport sector* indicator.

2) Denmark

Denmark is considered to be a pioneer in promoting sustainability, so it is no surprise that it ranks so highly. It has an impressive ranking on both the EPI and the GFI, 1st and 2nd place respectively.

However, it does rank relatively lower in terms of its CO2 emissions per capita and annual average PM2.5 concentration. At 31st place with **4.43 tonnes** for the former and at 16th place with **9.6 µg/m³** for the latter.

One of Denmark’s highlights is that it comes out on top for the EPI’s *wastewater treatment* indicator. Which means 100% of its population is connected to a sewer system and 100% of its household wastewater is treated.

3) United Kingdom

Despite its history the UK has been making headway in recent years as it aims to meet its **net zero target** by 2050. Ranking 2nd for the EPI and 4th for the GFI, it is clear that the UK is determined to make a greener future a reality.

Following closely with an EPI score of 77.7, the UK excels in ecosystem vitality and climate change mitigation despite its industrialized status. However, it still has some work to do in regards to its CO2 emissions and annual average PM2.5 concentration. It ranks in 34th place with **4.66 tonnes** for the former and in 13th place with **8.8 µg/m³** for the latter.

The UK performs particularly well for *climate policy*, ranking 3rd in the GFI and 2nd in the EPI for this category.

4) Finland

Finland ranks 3rd on the EPI and 6th on the GFI. In particular, Finland excels in the GFI’s *Clean Innovation* pillar, ranking first. Furthermore, it achieves

¹ The Environmental Performance Index (EPI) was developed by Yale University to rank which countries are best addressing environmental challenges. It uses 40 performance indicators relating to climate change performance, environmental health, and ecosystem vitality.

² The European Union’s Joint Research Centre looks at the fossil CO2 emissions of more than 200 countries and territories. It includes CO2 emissions per capita to account for population size.

³ The Green Future Index (GFI) by Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) ranks 76 nations and territories based on their progress and commitment towards a sustainable future. It examines 22 indicators across the following five pillars: climate policy, carbon emissions, energy transition, green society, and clean innovation.

⁴ IQAir provides the world’s largest free real-time air quality information platform to fight against air pollution. They provide data on the annual average PM2.5 concentration (µg/m³) for 117 countries and territories.

first place for the lowest annual average PM2.5 concentration with **5.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$** .

Out of the four studies, Finland mainly needs to focus on reducing its CO2 emissions, as it ranks 45th place with **7.29 tonnes** per capita. The nation is already implementing change and plans to **reduce its dependence on fossil fuels by 50% by 2030**.

5) Switzerland

Switzerland placed 9th on the EPI and 14th on the GFI. It scores relatively lower for its CO2 emissions per capita and annual average PM2.5 concentration. Ranking 27th with **4.07 tonnes** and 20th with **10.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$** , respectively.

Switzerland has a perfect score for both the EPI's *sanitation and drinking water* indicators, meaning it has among **the lowest DALY rates** (age-standardised disability-adjusted life-years lost per 100,000 persons) in the world. The country's goal to achieve 100% renewable energy by 2050 is a testament to its forward-thinking approach.

6) France

Next on the list is France, which ranks 12th on the EPI and 7th on the GFI. This nation produces **4.26 tonnes** of CO2 emissions per capita, meaning it comes in at 29th. Furthermore, France has an annual average PM2.5 concentration of **11.4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$** , making it 23rd on the list.

In 2015, France became an **early adopter of the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals**. Therefore, it's understandable why it ranks 4th place for the GFI's *Climate Policy* pillar.

7) Costa Rica

Costa Rica, the first non-European country on the list, is a true front-runner when it comes to creating a more sustainable future. It comes in 8th place for the lowest annual average PM2.5 concentrations with **7.8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$** . Furthermore, it ranks 12th with **1.55 tonnes** in regards to CO2 emissions per capita and 20th in the GFI.

However, out of the 180 nations assessed in the EPI, Costa Rica only places 68th. Despite this, the EPI still gave Costa Rica a perfect score for *SO2 growth rate*, meaning it's **cutting emissions by $\geq 3.94\%$ per year**.

8) Iceland

Iceland is considered to be the top nation by the GFI and ranks in 10th place in the EPI. It also has a low annual average PM2.5 concentration of **6.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$** , ranking 3rd place.

However, Iceland's CO2 emissions per capita have room for improvement as it ranks 56th with **9.23 tonnes**. The government plans to **achieve carbon neutrality by 2040 and be fossil-fuel-free by 2050**, so we should see Iceland moving up the rankings in the coming years.

9) Norway

Norway ranks 20th on the EPI and 5th on the GFI. According to the GFI, it is leading in the area of *Green Transport*. Norway has an annual average PM2.5 concentration of **7.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$** and **7.74 tonnes** of CO2 emissions per capita, making it rank in 7th and 49th place respectively.

In order to become even greener, Norway plans to **reduce 90-95% of its greenhouse gas emissions** (excluding sinks) from 1990 levels by 2050.

10) Ireland

Ireland comes in 24th place on the EPI and 12th on the GFI. A highlight being that it ranks 3rd on the GFI's *Green Society* pillar. Furthermore, Ireland ranks 9th for the lowest annual average PM2.5 concentrations with **8 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$** .

However, Ireland only ranks 41st in CO2 emissions per capita, with **6.68 tonnes**. To address this, the government has created a **Climate Action Plan which commits Ireland to reach net zero no later than 2050**.

Pic. 1 The World's Greenest Countries [6]

The bottom 10 greenest countries are as follows:

1) Qatar

Unfortunately, Qatar places last on our list of greenest countries. It ranks 137th on the EPI and 73rd on the GFI. Its annual average PM2.5 concentration is a worrying **38.2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$** , placing it 66th. Qatar also comes in last place for its CO2 emissions per capita with **35.64 tonnes**.

This is backed up by the UN's evaluation of Qatar's progress towards achieving the **Sustainable Development Goals**. In regards to goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and goal 13 (Climate Action), major challenges remain, and for goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), significant challenges still remain.

2) Iran

Iran also needs to improve in regards to its sustainability efforts. It only ranks 133rd on the EPI and 76th

on the GFI. In regards to CO₂ emissions per capita it ranks 52nd with **8.26 tonnes**, and for annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations it ranks 59th with **30.3 µg/m³**.

The Sustainable Development Report also assesses that major challenges still remain for Iran in regards to affordable and clean energy. Furthermore, for goals 11 and 13, Iran is assessed to be stagnating with significant challenges remaining.

3) Turkey

Turkey does not fare well on either the EPI or GFI, ranking 172nd and 69th place respectively. It also ranks 48th place for the lowest annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations with **20 µg/m³** and 35th place for CO₂ emissions per capita with **4.83 tonnes**.

This is confirmed by the Sustainable Development Report, that states challenges remain for affordable and clean energy, significant challenges remain for sustainable cities and communities, and major challenges remain for climate action.

4) China

China has quite a striking difference in where it ranks on the EPI compared to the GFI, 160th for the former and 26th for the latter. For annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations, it ranks 61st with **32.6 µg/m³**, and for CO₂ emissions per capita it ranks 51st with **8.2 tonnes**.

In regards to the Sustainable Development goals, (significant) challenges remain for China across goals 7, 11, and 13. However, it is moving in the right direction, as it is deemed to be “moderately increasing” across these goals.

5) Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia also has some way to go in regards to becoming more green. It ranks 109th on the EPI and 51st on the GFI. Its scores for annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations and CO₂ emissions per capita are also not great. Ranking 62nd with **32.7 µg/m³** for the former and 66th with **16.96 tonnes** for the latter.

Looking at the Sustainable Development Goals it is clear that both significant and major challenges remain for Saudi Arabia in regards to goals 7, 11, and 13. However, it has been assessed as “moderately increasing” across these goals, so hopefully there will be improvements in the near future.

6) Vietnam

Vietnam performs relatively well in regards to its CO₂ emissions per capita, ranking 21st with **3.27 tonnes**. However, its rankings across the other studies could do with a major boost. It ranks 178th on the EPI, 56th on the GFI, and 53rd for the lowest annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations with **24.7 µg/m³**.

According to the Sustainable Development Report, (significant) challenges remain for Vietnam in the areas of affordable and clean energy, sustainable cities and communities, and climate action.

7) Indonesia

Indonesia’s total carbon emissions are relatively high at **568.27 Mt**, however, due to its large population size it only produces **2.09 tonnes per capita**, leaving it in 17th place. Otherwise, Indonesia ranks quite poorly. It is 164th on the EPI and 70th on the GFI. In regards to the lowest annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations, it ranks 64th with **34.3 µg/m³**.

This is confirmed by the Sustainable Development Report, which states challenges still remain across goals 7, 11, and 13 for Indonesia. In particular for goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities).

8) Malaysia

Malaysia also ranks in the bottom ten for the greenest countries in the world. It comes in 130th place on the EPI and 65th on the GFI. It ranks 50th for CO₂ emissions per capita with **7.98 tonnes**, and 45th place for annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations with **19.4 µg/m³**.

This is backed up by the Sustainable Development Report, which states that challenges (of varying magnitudes) remain for Malaysia in regards to goals 7, 11, and 13.

9) Algeria

Algeria is another country in the bottom ten that ranks relatively well in terms of its CO₂ emissions per capita, in 23rd place with **3.77 tonnes**. However, it still has work to do in regards to the other metrics. It ranks 155th on the EPI, 75th on the GFI, and 47th on the lowest annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations with **20 µg/m³**.

In regards to the Sustainable Development goals, significant and major challenges remain for Algeria across goals 7, 11, and 13. In addition to this, for goal 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) it has even been deemed to be regressing.

10) Kuwait

Finally, we have Kuwait which ranks 61st out of the 69 countries on this list. It comes in 87th position for the EPI and 58th for the GFI. It has a rank of 68th for CO₂ emissions per capita with **20.91 tonnes** and ranks 58th for the lowest annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations with **29.7 µg/m³**.

Again, this is confirmed by the Sustainable Development Report, which assesses Kuwait to have significant and major challenges remaining across goals 7, 11, and 13.

Conclusions

Green Economy focuses on sustainable development by integrating environmental health, economic growth, and social equity, using innovative technologies and practices to reduce environmental impact and improve resource efficiency.

Brown Economy, on the other hand, prioritizes short-term economic growth often at the expense of environmental and social concerns, leading to significant ecological damage and resource depletion.

Transitioning from a brown economy to a green economy involves adopting sustainable practices, investing in green technologies, and implementing policies that support long-term environmental and social well-being.

As we move towards 2025, the focus on sustainable development only intensifies. Countries at the top of our list are expected to continue their leadership in green technologies and sustainable practices. However, dynamic changes in policies and global environmental conditions could influence future rankings.

Continuous monitoring and adaptation of policies are essential for maintaining and improving environmental performance.

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